

Teachers and Technology in Rural Malaysian Classrooms

Insights from the T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey

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Reviewers

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Abbreviations and acronyms

B40	The bottom 40% of Malaysian households by income
CEFR	Common European Framework of Reference for Languages
LMICs	Low- and middle-income countries
TPD	Teacher professional development

Executive summary

This technical report examines how teachers in rural Malaysian classrooms experienced and used educational technology during the Covid-19 pandemic, drawing on a secondary analysis of responses from 287 Malaysian teachers who participated in the T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey ([↑Pota et al., 2021](#)). Framed within broader debates on digital inequality and rural education, the report foregrounds structural and contextual factors shaping technology use, professional learning, and learners' experiences.

The findings show that rural teachers faced persistent infrastructural constraints, including unstable internet connectivity, limited access to devices, and insufficient institutional support. In response, teachers demonstrated adaptive professionalism by prioritising low-bandwidth and widely accessible tools such as messaging applications, short instructional videos, and printed materials. These practices reflect pragmatic pedagogical decision-making aligned with learners' material realities, rather than limited digital competence. Comparative analysis across rural, suburban, and urban contexts indicates that rural teachers were less able to implement interaction-intensive digital practices, largely due to structural constraints rather than pedagogical resistance.

The report also highlights strong professional motivation among rural teachers, many of whom engaged in self-initiated or free teacher professional development despite limited formal support. Teachers identified a need for context-sensitive professional development that supports low-bandwidth pedagogies, curricular adaptation, and greater professional autonomy. Teachers' perceptions of learners' needs further reveal that learning loss was shaped by socioeconomic disadvantage, household constraints, and unequal access to technology.

The report concludes with recommendations for context-responsive professional development, increased curricular flexibility, and sustained structural investment. While grounded in Malaysia, the findings offer transferable insights for rural and resource-constrained settings across low- and middle-income countries, contributing to the equity-focused evidence base of EdTech Hub.

1. Introduction

1.1. Preamble: A reflection on digital inequalities

During the Covid-19 pandemic, a video of a teenage girl spending the night in a makeshift treehouse in the rural Malaysian jungle to get internet access for her online lessons went viral, and her story made it to the BBC News ([↑BBC World Service, 2020](#); [↑Tse, 2020](#)). Sadly, this student's experience is not unique. In areas where resources are scarce, and internet access is almost nonexistent, thousands of learners struggle to keep up with learning every day, not just during a pandemic. This story, along with those depicted in the news headlines in [Figure 1a](#), made it clear to many that the pandemic was exacerbating problems related to resource scarcity and digital inequality. For example, [↑Beaunoyer et al. \(2020\)](#) argue that the Covid-19 crisis intensified pre-existing digital inequalities by placing additional pressure on already scarce technological and connectivity resources.

Figure 1a. News headlines presenting challenges faced by learners in Malaysia during the Covid-19 pandemic. Sources: [↑Malay Mail, 2020](#); [↑Miwil, 2020](#); [↑Tse, 2020](#)

In the Malaysian context, [↑Devisakti et al. \(2024\)](#) conducted a qualitative study of higher education students from the bottom 40% of households in terms of income, representing the lowest-income socioeconomic group used in national policy and education research (also referred to as the 'B40'). The study documents concrete resource scarcity, including a lack of personal devices, insufficient storage, limited internet connectivity, bandwidth problems, and affordability constraints. The findings also show

how these scarcities translate directly into digital inequality in participation, engagement, and achievement during the pandemic. For example, it appeared that students were frequently missing classes or turning in assignments late because their devices and connections were unable to handle the demands of online learning.

This report aims to understand the specific needs of learners affected by digital disparities in Malaysia by analysing the results of the T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey ([↑Pota et al., 2021](#)). It also seeks to identify the challenges faced by Malaysian teachers who struggle to meet the unique needs of these learners. In addition, this report explores how teacher professional development could support teachers and students in this particular context.

The report begins by outlining Malaysia's education situation during the pandemic, including how the government handled issues like school closures and other mitigation measures. It then reviews the current literature on rural education and teacher professional development (TPD) in rural settings, followed by an outline of the objectives and research questions, and an overview of the survey. The main section of the report is dedicated to data analysis and insights from the key findings. The report concludes with practical and pedagogical recommendations for implementing the TPD curriculum and providing institutional support.

1.2. Covid-19 and Malaysian education

On 16 March 2020, the Malaysian government implemented the first Movement Control Order to curb the spread of Covid-19. This situation limited the movement of its citizens in public places. The Order went through a series of stages in which restrictions were either loosened or tightened depending on how severe the virus was and how quickly it spread in different parts of Malaysia ([↑Rodzi, 2021](#); [↑Teoh, 2021](#)). Due to movement restrictions, schools across Malaysia experienced periodic closures. After a year of closures and reopenings, schools across the country resumed full operations in mid-April 2021, implementing safety and health protocols.

The Malaysian Ministry of Education issued a series of guidelines for educational institutions and teachers to follow during school closures to coordinate and carry out remote teaching. Four main strategies were implemented to ensure educational continuity during the Covid-19 pandemic, including flexible class schedules and pedagogies, online

classes, collaboration with mass media, and digital learning communities for professional development ([↑Izhar et al., 2021](#)).

The Ministry of Education also partnered with UNICEF to create online materials and training programmes to support teachers in conducting online teaching and learning. This partnership fell under the Digital Learning Teachers Community initiative and was part of the broader strategy for enhancing teacher professional development. The objective was to streamline the process, so teachers could create their own online classes and use Google Education tools. Through this partnership with UNICEF, five modules were created to assist educators in adapting to the emerging online teaching landscape ([↑UNICEF, 2020](#)).

Additionally, the Ministry of Education collaborated with the Ministry of Communication and Multimedia and media partners to expand the use of educational television as an alternative delivery mode for teaching and learning. Early efforts included the broadcast of TV Pendidikan (Educational TV) programmes on TV Okey, a channel owned by RTM, the Malaysian government's television station. During the Movement Control Order, TV Pendidikan targeted students from rural and marginalised communities who lacked access to digital devices or stable internet connectivity. Building on this initiative, the Ministry of Education later launched DidikTV KPM, a dedicated educational television channel offering curriculum-aligned lessons across multiple platforms, including free-to-air television. These initiatives reflect a policy-level recognition that online learning alone was insufficient to ensure equitable access to education and that broadcast media could play a critical role in sustaining learning continuity for digitally underserved learners during the pandemic ([↑Bernama, 2020](#); [↑Rajendram, 2021](#)).

[↑Izhar et al. \(2021\)](#) shed light on several challenges that remote teaching and learning faced during the pandemic. The presumption that students are technologically literate for academic purposes, the lack of consideration for parents' or caretakers' roles, and students' dissatisfaction with the lack of human interaction in the online learning environment were some of the difficulties reported by Malaysian educators in online teaching and learning. To tackle these obstacles, it was suggested that parents be involved in student discipline management, that educators be provided with training to equip them for pedagogical shifts, and students be granted access to necessary infrastructure, including internet connectivity and electronic devices. Additionally, the introduction of teacher training programmes and the provision of online resources and

training to assist educators in facilitating online teaching and learning were proposed as methods to cultivate support for both students and teachers ([Izhar et al., 2021](#)).

1.3. A focus on rural schools and teachers

Malaysian research during and after the Covid-19 pandemic exposes how rural learners' needs are shaped not simply by geography, but also by enduring structural inequities embedded in the national education system. Studies from rural Sabah and Sarawak (East Malaysia), for example, show that students' specific needs arise from unstable connectivity, device scarcity, overcrowded households, and reliance on low-tech or offline learning modes. These conditions severely limited participation in the online curriculum during school closures ([Saidi et al., 2022](#); [Yap et al., 2024](#)).

However, the responsibility for addressing these systemic deficiencies was often shifted onto rural teachers, who themselves lacked adequate infrastructure, reliable internet access, and institutional support to enact the forms of digital pedagogy demanded by pandemic-era policy. This mismatch between policy expectations and ground realities reveals a longstanding centre-periphery divide in which rural schools remain structurally underserved despite decades of reform rhetoric ([Daar & Nasar, 2021](#); [Yap et al., 2024](#)). While TPD is frequently framed as a solution, the literature cautions that urban-centric, technology-heavy TPD models risk reinforcing inequalities when they ignore the material constraints of rural areas, such as limited bandwidth, sporadic electricity, and the uneven rollout of digital infrastructure, which is common in many parts of East Malaysia ([Coker, 2021](#); [Huang et al., 2024](#); [Singh et al., 2025](#)).

Critical analyses argue that only TPD programmes that are context-sensitive, community-embedded, and aligned with the technologies and resources that teachers can realistically access show meaningful impact on instructional practice and learner outcomes ([Coker, 2021](#); [Huang et al., 2024](#)). Collectively, evidence from research suggests that without confronting systemic resource disparities and rethinking policy implementation through a rural equity lens, professional development reforms and digital initiatives may unintentionally reproduce the very inequalities they aim to resolve. Echoing global TPD research findings, local studies ([Kabilan, 2019](#); [Lee & James, 2018](#)) indicate that the most significant issues surrounding TPD in Malaysia are:

- A lack of focus on teachers' professional requirements and interests;
- Disregard for the specific needs of the students in their setting;
- The use of culturally inappropriate curricular materials.

In addition, teachers in rural schools in indigenous communities often lack access to professional development opportunities due to their scattered geographical locations ([↑James et al., 2022](#); [↑Kumarsir & Shah, 2020](#)).

A comprehensive systematic review by [↑Hennessy et al. \(2022\)](#) found comparable results regarding the use of technology to enhance TPD in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs). The analysis highlights the difficulties educators in rural, low-resource contexts face, including inadequate qualifications and limited availability of impactful professional development opportunities. Additionally, the review emphasises that when opportunities are readily available, they often lack practical applications, are overly theoretical, and have little connection to real-life classroom scenarios. [↑Hennessy et al. \(2022\)](#) also examine the capacity of technology-facilitated TPD to reduce disparities and amplify autonomy, while emphasising the significance of interpersonal connections in the realm of technology-assisted professional development. They explore effective, tailored methods for using technology to support the professional development of teachers in LMICs, including the potential of virtual coaching, social messaging, and blended learning to meet the specific requirements of teachers and learners in these contexts.

The literature points to TPD in rural contexts as a structurally situated challenge shaped by systemic inequities rather than individual teacher deficits. Persistent misalignments between dominant professional development models and rural teachers' professional needs, learners' realities, and cultural contexts raise questions about the relevance and effectiveness of existing approaches. Although technology is often promoted as a solution to geographical isolation, its capacity to support meaningful professional learning remains uneven and highly dependent on infrastructural conditions and opportunities for professional interaction. These tensions provide an opportunity to critically examine how technology-facilitated professional development is experienced and constrained in rural teaching contexts.

1.4. 'Rural schools': Definitions and characteristics

It is important to provide a working definition of the key term 'rural school' for this report, as it has been defined in various ways by many scholars ([↑Marwan et al., 2012](#)). [↑Herzog & Pittman \(1995\)](#) define 'rural' as an area that is not part of a city or a non-metropolitan area, or, quite simply, as the opposite of 'urban'. The term 'rural school' is commonly used to describe educational establishments in rural regions, characterised by their remoteness from urban hubs, limited resource availability, and smaller student enrolments ([↑Renganathan, 2023](#)). These schools frequently cater to populations facing distinctive obstacles, such as poverty, inadequate infrastructure, and the struggle to attract highly skilled teachers. Additionally, rural schools are often characterised by isolation, long distances between places, and smaller student populations ([↑Malhoit, 2005](#); [↑Shikalepo, 2020](#)).

Rural education refers to the educational practices implemented in schools in rural regions, which often face distinctive challenges such as economic hardship, limited resources, and higher rates of teacher attrition ([↑Zhenhua, 2023](#)). These schools accommodate a heterogeneous student body, comprising individuals from low-income households, first-generation college seekers, and members of ethnic and racial minority groups, reflecting broader patterns of socioeconomic and cultural diversity in rural education ([↑Cain et al., 2024](#)). Rural schools frequently have distinct challenges, including scarce finances, difficulties recruiting and retaining highly skilled educators, and restricted access to cutting-edge educational technologies ([↑Evans & Mendez Acosta, 2023](#)). Students residing in rural areas frequently endure deplorable conditions of poverty and malnutrition because of their families' inability to furnish fundamental necessities ([↑Shikalepo, 2020](#)). Rural schools also face challenges due to insufficient resources, which affect students' academic progress and the school's capacity to deliver a high-quality education ([↑Volmer, 2023](#)).

[↑Renganathan's \(2023\)](#) systematic review of English language education in rural schools in Malaysia corroborates conclusions from international studies on education in isolated, resource-limited regions. Funding shortages, dilapidated school buildings, difficulties in recruiting and retaining highly skilled teachers, and inadequate facilities and resources are cited in the review as the most significant obstacles. Additionally, the review highlights grey literature showing how students in Malaysian states with a higher proportion of rural schools, specifically Sabah and Sarawak, perform less well academically than students in states with a lower

proportion of rural schools (see [↑Cambridge Assessment English, 2013](#); [↑Ministry of Education Malaysia, 2013](#)).

The Ministry of Education divides public schools in Malaysia into three broad categories: urban, suburban, and rural. Rural schools in Malaysia are further categorised into three types: Type 1, Type 2, and Type 3. These classifications are based on criteria associated with the availability of basic facilities and infrastructure, such as modes of transportation, travel-related risks, electricity, accommodation, sanitation, telecommunications, health facilities, water supply, and other basic amenities such as banks, post offices, and public places of worship. [Table 1](#) below outlines the characteristics of Type 1, Type 2, and Type 3 government schools in rural areas of Malaysia, as specified by the Ministry of Education.

Table 1. Classifications of rural school categories in Malaysia. Source: Translated from Malay into English from Sabah State Education Department Circular No. 1/2017. The original table (in Malay) has also been republished in [Haji Mohd Zeki et al. \(2020\)](#).

Facilities	Descriptions		
	Rural Type 1	Rural Type 2	Rural Type 3
1 The number of transportation modes required to reach the school from the nearest town	Only one mode of transportation is required, travel costs are low (typically below MYR 50), and the distance to the closest town is less than 70 km.	Two modes of transportation are required, or only one if the cost of travel is high (more than MYR 100 for a one-way trip). The distance to the closest town may also be a determining factor (more than 70 km but less than 100 km).	Three or more modes of transportation are required, and travel costs are high (more than MYR150); or one or two transportation modes are required, and travel costs are exceptionally high. The distance to the closest town is more than 100 km, but it could be less if travelling on log roads or trails.
2 Travel-related risks	One or two travel-related risks, such as steep/slippery roads or risks of landslides.	Two travel-related risks, such as floods or rapids.	More than three travel-related risks, such as large waves, animals, and/or pirate attacks.
3 Electricity	Electricity is available 24 hours or at least 12 hours a day (powered by public or private sources).	Electricity is available for at least 12 hours a day (powered by public or private sources) or via generator sets.	Electricity is supplied by generator sets, solar power, or there is none at all.
4 Accommodation available for teachers/school staffs	Housing quarters in accordance with certified plans and standards are available.	Only makeshift or substandard accommodation is available.	Modified accommodation (e.g., repurposed from classrooms, storage rooms, etc.) or no accommodation at all.

Facilities	Descriptions		
	Rural Type 1	Rural Type 2	Rural Type 3
5 Sanitation	Modern/flushing toilets are available.	Some form of flushing toilet is available (e.g., toilets are flushed manually using a bucket of water).	Only non-flushing toilets are available (e.g., pit latrines, bucket toilets, or 'open' toilets).
6 Telecommunications	Fixed-line/cellular services for telephone and/or internet connection are available.	Telecommunications are dependent on satellite systems or Automatic Telephone Using Radio (ATUR).	Telecommunications are dependent on Automatic Telephone Using Radio (ATUR), or there are no telecommunications services at all.
7 Health services	At least one rural health service, e.g., a rural clinic/moving clinic/flying doctor, is available.	At least one rural health service, e.g., a rural clinic/moving clinic/flying doctor, is available.	There is no available health service.

The problems faced by schools in rural areas highlight the need to implement targeted interventions, provide additional support, allocate resources to meet the distinct needs of rural schools, and ensure fair and equal access to high-quality education in these regions. In this regard, it is worth noting that rural schools also have certain benefits that distinguish them from metropolitan schools. These assets include reduced classroom sizes, increased teacher–student interaction, the implementation of progressive curricula such as place-based education, and the cultivation of a strong sense of community values and identity. [↑Volmer \(2023\)](#) asserts that comprehending the benefits and drawbacks of rural schools can guarantee a comprehensive, community-oriented, and academically successful educational setting. This argument is further supported by the Learning from the Extremes initiative, which highlights the importance of addressing educational inequities by building on the cultural values, local knowledge, and contextual resources of marginalised and rural schools, as well as the Why Rural Matters 2023 report, which similarly emphasises that empowering rural learners depends on leveraging community strengths, personalised learning approaches, and locally grounded support structures rather than relying solely on standardised solutions ([↑Learning from the Extremes, no date](#); [↑Showalter, et al., 2023](#)). These perspectives suggest that interventions for rural education must move beyond deficit-based models to contextually responsive approaches that recognise both structural constraints and existing community assets. Guided by this premise, this report examines how targeted professional development and pedagogical support can be designed to respond to the lived realities of rural schools, thereby informing the research objectives and questions that follow.

The literature reviewed above highlights several persistent tensions in rural education during the Covid-19 pandemic. While technology was widely promoted as a means of sustaining learning continuity and supporting TPD, its effectiveness in rural contexts was highly uneven and strongly mediated by infrastructural conditions, household-level inequalities, and institutional support. Research from Malaysia and comparable LMIC contexts shows that rural teachers frequently adapted their pedagogical practices to these constraints, often relying on low-bandwidth tools and informal professional networks rather than the platforms and models assumed in policy-driven or urban-centric approaches. At the same time, existing studies point to misalignments between dominant professional development models, curriculum expectations, and the lived realities of rural classrooms, raising concerns about equity, feasibility, and

sustainability. However, there remains limited empirical evidence that foregrounds teachers' own perspectives on these challenges across rural, suburban, and urban contexts within Malaysia. In this context, a focused analysis of Malaysian teachers' survey responses provides an opportunity to examine how technological constraints, professional development needs, and perceptions of learners' needs intersect in rural settings, thereby motivating the research objectives and questions that follow.

1.5. Objectives and research questions

Teachers' responses to the Covid-19 pandemic offer insightful perspectives on the types of technologies deemed most useful by teachers in rural and resource-scarce areas. For example, the large-scale T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey, which involved 20,679 teachers from 165 countries, pointed to mobile chat apps such as WhatsApp and the use of recorded videos as the most popular mode of instruction delivery among teachers in these contexts ([Pota et al., 2021](#); see also [Jordan, 2023](#)). This report presents a secondary analysis of the data, concentrating on 287 responses from Malaysian teachers.¹ It aims to achieve the following objectives:

Objective 1: To identify the challenges to using technology faced by teachers in rural areas in Malaysia.

Objective 2: To identify the types of technology available for teachers and learners and the types of technology deemed most useful by teachers in rural areas in Malaysia.

Objective 3: To determine how teachers in rural areas in Malaysia might be supported through professional development.

Objective 4: To identify Malaysian teachers' perceptions of the specific needs of learners in rural areas during the Covid-19 pandemic.

¹ T4 survey data from teachers in Tanzania, Pakistan, and India have also been analysed separately, by [Koomar et al. \(2022\)](#); [Raza & Hennessy \(2025\)](#), and [Tailor et al. \(2022\)](#) respectively.

The research questions are:

Research question 1: What technological challenges do teachers in rural areas in Malaysia face?

Research question 2: What are the types of technology available for teachers and learners, and the types of technology deemed most useful by teachers in rural areas in Malaysia?

Research question 3: How could professional development support teachers in Malaysia's rural areas?

Research question 4: What are Malaysian teachers' perceptions of the specific needs of learners in rural areas during the pandemic?

2. Methodology

2.1. The T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey

As mentioned, this report utilises data from the T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey, which included over 20,000 teachers ([Pota et al., 2021](#)). The purpose of the large-scale survey was to gather teachers' responses to the Covid-19 pandemic in relation to teaching with technology. The comprehensive dataset contains extensive metrics on teachers' utilisation of digital tools and resources, the digital infrastructure of their respective schools, and their participation in professional development programmes for remote learning from May 2020 to April 2021. This makes it an optimal resource for this report's purposes. The [Appendix](#) includes the entire questionnaire, with the specific questions examined for this study highlighted in bold. The survey was translated into multiple languages, including Malay, and teachers' open-ended responses were also made in Malay.

Using descriptive statistics, this report presents an analysis of responses from 287 Malaysian teachers who participated in the survey. This analysis concentrates on four key areas:

1. The technological challenges faced by teachers in rural areas.
2. The types of technology available to teachers and learners, and the types of technology deemed most useful by teachers in rural areas.
3. The professional development needs of teachers in rural areas.
4. Teachers' perceptions of learners' specific needs in rural areas during the pandemic.

To enhance transparency and replicability, [Figure 1b](#) provides an overview of the data extraction and analytical process used in this study. The analysis draws on a secondary subset of responses from Malaysian teachers within the T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey. Following identification of the Malaysian sample, responses were categorised by school location (rural, suburban, and urban) based on teachers' self-reported school context. Relevant survey items were then selected to address the four research questions, focusing on technology access and use, teaching practices during the pandemic, TPD, and teachers'

perceptions of learners' needs. The analysis employed descriptive statistics and comparisons across school locations to identify patterns and differences, which are reported in [Section 3](#) through figures and interpretive commentary.

Figure 1b. Overview of data extraction and analytical process

This figure illustrates the process used to extract and analyse Malaysian responses from the T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey. Responses from teachers in Malaysia ($n = 287$) were identified from the full global dataset and categorised by school location (rural, suburban, and urban). Survey items relevant to technology access and use, teaching practices, TPD, and perceptions of learners' needs were selected for secondary analysis. Descriptive statistics and comparative analyses across school locations were then conducted to generate the findings and insights presented in this report.

2.2. The regions: 'rural', 'urban', and 'suburban'

The first item in the 'About Your School' section of the questionnaire asks the question: *What type of area is your school located in?* Select one answer. The following options are listed as responses:

1 – City/Urban/Metropolitan Area

2 – Rural Area

3 – Town/Semi-dense Area/Suburbs

For conciseness, this report refers to Option 1 as ‘urban area’ (or ‘urban school’), Option 2 as ‘rural area’ (or ‘rural school’), and Option 3 as ‘suburban area’ (or ‘suburban school’).

2.3. Participants’ background and contexts

The teachers who participated in the T4 survey represented a balanced geographic spread, with 31% teaching in urban schools, 34% in rural schools, and 35% in suburban areas (see [Figure 2](#) below). This near-even distribution strengthens the comparative insights of this report, particularly when examining differences in technological access, curriculum needs, and perceptions of learning loss across school locations. In terms of subject specialisation, language teachers formed the largest group, followed by science and mathematics teachers (see [Figure 3](#) below). This composition is noteworthy because these subjects were among the most impacted by shifts to online and hybrid learning, where interaction, feedback, and scaffolding play critical roles.

Figure 2. Locations of schools

Figure 3. Subjects taught by teachers

The participants were also predominantly highly experienced educators. Over 60% had more than 10 years of teaching experience, with teachers in the largest group (33%) having 21–30 years of service, and another 31% having 11–20 years of service (see Figure 4). Only a small proportion (9%) had less than 5 years of experience. This demographic profile suggests that the findings largely reflect the perspectives of seasoned practitioners who are deeply familiar with their learners, school communities, and systemic constraints. Their insights, therefore, carry significant weight in understanding the complex challenges of rural education, the realities of curriculum implementation, and the types of professional development that are genuinely needed.

Figure 4. Years of school teaching experience

2.4. Limitations of the survey

Publicity on networks and social media accounts affiliated with the authoring organisations (primarily T4 Education and EdTech Hub) and their global partners was used to generate the sample, with the aim of reaching as many government schools in LMICs as possible with the survey. Therefore, the sampling methodology employed was neither systematic nor representative; instead, it comprised a combination of purposive, convenience, and snowball sampling ([Pota et al., 2021](#)). The lengthy survey resulted in a low completion rate: 27% (or $n = 77$) of the total number of responses included in this analysis ($n = 287$) commenced the survey but did not finish it.

Furthermore, as noted by [Pota et al. \(2021\)](#) there is certainly a level of selection bias in the survey results because only teachers with access to technology and internet connectivity could respond in its digital format. Those without access were unable to participate. Teachers who possess a keen interest in technology may also have been more likely to discover the survey, such as through social media platforms, and to be more driven to complete it.

While the analytical process is transparent and replicable, findings remain bounded by the structure and scope of the original survey instrument.

3. Findings

This section presents the findings from the survey analysis, organised according to the four research questions that shaped the investigation. The results are summarised with supporting data and a brief interpretive commentary to highlight key patterns in teachers' experiences, technological conditions, professional development needs, and learners' challenges in rural contexts.

3.1. Technological challenges faced by teachers in rural areas

RQ1: What technological challenges do teachers in rural areas of Malaysia face?

Figures 5 to 8 below collectively illustrate the multi-layered digital and infrastructural inequities shaping rural teaching and learning contexts. [Figure 5](#) shows that teachers identified insufficient internet access as the most significant hindrance to delivering quality instruction, indicating that connectivity issues remain a systemic constraint rather than an incidental inconvenience.

Figure 5. *Top hindrances to providing quality instruction during the pandemic*

The pattern is further contextualised in [Figure 6](#), which shows that rural teachers reported substantially greater difficulties with technical support and school infrastructure than their suburban and urban counterparts. This disparity suggests that digital disadvantage in rural schools extends beyond weak connectivity, reflecting broader institutional gaps that inhibit teachers' capacity to enact digital or blended pedagogies.

Figure 6. *Top 3 hindrances to providing quality instruction in rural areas*

[Figure 7](#) further reveals that 40% of rural teachers rely on their personal devices to conduct classroom instruction, highlighting an under-recognised form of resource substitution whereby individual teachers compensate for infrastructure deficits at their own expense. This reliance points to a serious disparity between policy expectations and the actual material conditions in which rural teachers work.

Figure 7. Availability of digital devices in schools

Finally, [Figure 8](#) presents selected open-ended responses from teachers (translated from Malay into English by the first author), providing qualitative insights into how learners and their families experience these structural limitations. The statements demonstrate that the digital divide is not purely technical but also socioeconomic and relational, reflecting challenges such as unreliable internet connectivity, limited digital literacy, and the need to share devices among siblings. Together, the four figures portray a coherent pattern: rural educational challenges during and after the Covid-19 pandemic are structurally embedded, affecting both teachers' instructional capacities and students' opportunities for equitable participation.

Figure 8. Challenges faced by learners in rural areas

3.2. The types of technology available and deemed most useful in rural areas

RQ2: What are the types of technology available to teachers and learners, and the types of technology deemed most useful by teachers in the rural areas of Malaysia?

Figures 9 and 10 provide complementary insights into the types of technology rural teachers relied on during the Covid-19 pandemic and the tools they perceived as most pedagogically valuable, revealing patterns that are shaped as much by infrastructural constraints as by pedagogical intent.

Figure 9 shows that rural teachers reported lower use of bandwidth-intensive synchronous tools such as online teaching platforms compared to their urban peers, while relying more heavily on messaging services, instructional videos, and printed copies of digital materials. This pattern implies that rural educators were deliberately choosing resources that matched the material realities of their students, especially the need to reach students asynchronously or through low-bandwidth channels, sporadic internet access, and limited device ownership. These modifications are consistent with broader research demonstrating that educators in digitally limited environments frequently favour technologies that provide adaptability, accessibility, and resilience in the face of

infrastructural stress (↑Esteban-Navarro et al., 2020; ↑Valencia-Arias et al., 2025).

Figure 9. Most frequent activities undertaken during the Covid-19 pandemic

Figure 10 reinforces this interpretation by highlighting which technologies rural teachers considered most useful. Ranked first is ‘messaging and social media’ (80%), followed closely by ‘video resources’ (77%), and to a lesser extent, ‘video-conferencing tools’ (59%). These preferences highlight a crucial realisation for TPD design: that a tool’s usefulness is not only determined by its pedagogical richness but also by its compatibility with rural infrastructure and ease of use by students. For example, social media and messaging apps are familiar to families, have low bandwidth requirements, and can facilitate both pastoral care and educational communication. Teachers can provide repeatable, asynchronous explanations using video resources, which are especially useful for

students who have to share devices or have trouble connecting to the internet.

Figure 10. *Digital tools that rural teachers found most useful*

Together, these figures suggest that effective TPD for rural teachers must be grounded in an understanding of the technological ecologies in which rural teaching takes place. Rather than promoting high-bandwidth, urban-centric tools, TPD should prioritise helping teachers maximise the pedagogical potential of technologies they already use and trust, such as messaging platforms, short instructional videos, and hybrid paper / digital materials. Furthermore, TPD should incorporate strategies for designing low-bandwidth content, managing asynchronous instruction, supporting parents' engagement via mobile-friendly channels, and adapting lessons for contexts where learners share devices or experience frequent disruptions. In this sense, the findings challenge deficit narratives about rural teachers' technology use and instead highlight their context-responsive, pragmatic decision-making, pointing towards a model of TPD that is asset-based, context-sensitive, and explicitly attuned to infrastructural realities.

3.3. Support for teachers in rural areas through professional development

RQ3: How could professional development support teachers in Malaysia's rural areas?

Together, [Figures 11](#) and [12](#) below illustrate teachers' engagement in TPD during the pandemic, highlighting both high levels of participation and uneven patterns of support. Despite the challenges posed by Covid-19, a substantial proportion of teachers reported taking part in TPD activities in the preceding 12 months, suggesting a strong desire for professional learning even under crisis conditions. The prevalence of free TPD opportunities further indicates that many teachers, particularly those in rural and resource-constrained contexts, relied on self-sourced or externally provided training rather than institutionally funded programmes. This pattern points to teachers' resourcefulness and agency in navigating limited formal support while striving to sustain instructional quality. At the same time, the relatively small proportion of TPD costs fully covered by schools raises concerns about the equity and sustainability of professional learning provision, especially for rural teachers who may face greater financial and infrastructural constraints. The focus of TPD activities on digital tools and pedagogies for online or remote teaching reflects a pragmatic response to pandemic-related disruptions. It also suggests that professional development during this period was largely reactive, prioritising immediate instructional continuity over longer-term, context-responsive capacity building for rural education.

Figure 11. Funding for TPD activities

Figure 12. Focus of TPD during the Covid-19 pandemic

Figures 13 and 14 together illustrate not only the areas in which rural teachers make comparatively less use of digital tools, but also the kinds of support they identify as necessary for strengthening their digital teaching practices.

Figure 13 shows that rural teachers reported lower daily use of digital resources for student collaboration (45%) and providing feedback (52%) than their urban (60–61%) and suburban (51–60%) counterparts. This disparity suggests that rural teachers are less able to integrate higher-order, interactional uses of technology, such as collaborative learning and timely formative feedback. This is likely due to infrastructural constraints, such as an unstable internet, limited devices, and the need to prioritise low-bandwidth, individualised modes of instruction. The pattern aligns with broader research showing that teachers in digitally underserved contexts often restrict technology use to communication and content delivery, rather than more participatory or interactive pedagogies because the latter depend on reliable connectivity and consistent learner access (↑[Esteban-Navarro et al., 2020](#); ↑[Guillén-Gámez & Mayorga-Fernández, 2022](#)).

Figure 14 further highlights the specific professional development needs that teachers associate with improving their practice. Their top priorities are building skills and confidence in using digital technologies (16%), online / remote teaching (13%), and integrating technology into classroom practice (12%). These indicate that teachers are not resistant to digital innovation. Rather, they are seeking targeted, context-aware support to move beyond basic use.

Figure 13. Use of digital resources among teachers

Figure 14. Areas of support that teachers need

Taken together, the Figures 13 and 14 suggest that effective TPD for rural teachers must extend beyond generic digital skills training. It must explicitly address the structural barriers that make collaborative and feedback-oriented digital practices more difficult in rural contexts and provide practical, low-bandwidth strategies that are feasible within the technological realities. In this sense, the findings emphasise that rural teachers' professional development needs are qualitatively different, not merely quantitatively lower, than those of teachers in urban and suburban areas. Thus, this requires TPD that is situated, responsive, and grounded in the material conditions of rural schooling.

Additionally, teachers feel that post-pandemic recovery calls for more than just reviewing missed material, as shown in [Figure 15](#). It entails redefining educational experiences to emphasise autonomy, greater involvement, and meaningful engagement. A desire to foster learner autonomy is indicated by the most frequently recommended action, which is assisting students in understanding how to learn more effectively and creating independent learning strategies (11%). Limited access to digital tools, parental support, or stable learning environments may have caused rural learners to struggle more acutely in this area. Teachers also called for greater freedom in lesson planning (9%), signalling that rigid curricular structures may constrain their ability to tailor instruction to learners' varying readiness levels, especially in rural contexts, where learning gaps may be wider and resources more unevenly distributed. The emphasis on enhanced practice, reflection, and peer-to-peer learning (8–9%) also facilitates a transition towards pedagogies that promote enduring, collaborative, and learner-centred engagement. TPD will need to specifically model and modify these approaches for rural areas with low bandwidth or mixed modalities.

Figure 15. *What schools should do to help learners catch up*

Figure 16 below additionally highlights a distinctive trend among educators in rural areas: 41% of rural respondents regarded curriculum revision as essential, surpassing the proportions observed among suburban (35%) and urban (24%) educators. This heightened call for curriculum change suggests that rural teachers perceive the existing curriculum as misaligned with their learners' post-pandemic needs, possibly due to assumptions about technological access, lesson pacing, or the feasibility of implementing certain pedagogical expectations under resource constraints. For TPD design, this finding is especially instructive. It indicates that supporting rural teachers cannot focus solely on developing teaching techniques. Instead, TPD must engage with the broader curricular pressures teachers navigate, equipping them to interpret, adapt, and sometimes negotiate curriculum requirements in ways that are realistic for their contexts. In this sense, the combined insights from Figures 14 and 15 above point to effective TPD as agency-enhancing, contextually grounded, and responsive to both pedagogical and curricular dimensions of rural teachers' work.

Figure 16. Breakdown by location of respondents who felt a curriculum revision is necessary

Figures 17 and 18 illustrate teachers' use of digital technologies to collaborate with colleagues and their participation in online professional communities of practice over the past 12 months, revealing important contrasts across rural, urban, and suburban contexts. The data shows that teachers were highly engaged professionally across all locations, suggesting that they wanted to interact with their peers and learn together during and after the pandemic. Rural teachers reported frequent use of digital resources to share ideas with colleagues, with substantial proportions indicating weekly or daily engagement. This pattern challenges deficit-oriented assumptions that rural teachers are less digitally engaged, instead pointing to strong professional motivation and adaptive use of available technologies despite structural constraints.

Figure 17. Teachers' use of digital resources to share ideas or resources with colleagues

Figure 18. Teachers' participation in online communities of practice

At the same time, differences in the intensity and regularity of engagement suggest contextual variation in how professional collaboration is enacted. While suburban teachers were most likely to report daily or near-daily sharing of resources and participation in online communities, rural teachers' engagement tended to cluster around weekly participation. This may reflect the realities of rural teaching conditions, where intermittent connectivity, heavier workloads, or limited institutional support constrain sustained online interaction, even when motivation is high. The very low proportion of rural teachers who reported 'never or almost never' engaging in online communities further suggests that non-participation is not the dominant pattern. Rather, rural teachers appear committed to remaining professionally connected, albeit in ways shaped by context.

These findings suggest that rural teachers are not only willing but actively seeking collegial support, shared expertise, and professional dialogue, often through informal or self-initiated digital means. This aligns with broader evidence in the report that rural teachers frequently compensate for limited formal support through personal agency and peer networks. However, the data also highlights a critical implication for teacher professional development: reliance on voluntary, digitally mediated collaboration risks reinforcing inequities if systemic barriers, such as unreliable infrastructure, time constraints, or lack of recognition remain unaddressed. Effective TPD for rural contexts must therefore build on teachers' demonstrated motivation and collaborative practices while providing structural support, protected time, and context-responsive platforms that enable sustained professional communities to flourish alongside, rather than in spite of, challenging conditions.

3.4. Specific needs of learners in rural areas

RQ4: What are Malaysian teachers' perceptions of the specific needs of learners in rural areas during the pandemic?

Figure 19 below, illustrates a clear socioeconomic stratification across school locations, with rural teachers reporting markedly higher proportions of learners from low-income households (53%) compared to urban (21%) and suburban schools (31%). This socioeconomic distribution is not merely a demographic characteristic but a central determinant of learners' educational vulnerability during the pandemic. Teachers' perceptions in Figures 19 and 20 show that the challenges experienced by rural learners were structurally produced, stemming from poverty-related constraints

that limited access to devices, internet connectivity, and supportive home learning environments. Thus, teachers' accounts indicate that rural learners' needs were not generic pedagogical needs but needs arising from resource scarcity, competing household demands, and unstable learning conditions.

Figure 19. *Socioeconomic status of learners*

Figure 20 further sharpens this picture by revealing the ways family dynamics intersect with socioeconomic disadvantage. Rural teachers perceived that learners from larger households experienced greater learning loss, with 70% identifying children with many siblings as disproportionately affected. This suggests that digital inequity within households, such as device sharing, bandwidth limitations, and lack of quiet learning spaces, intensified the disadvantages faced by rural learners. Similarly, 36% of teachers observed that parents prioritised the learning of older children, indicating that economic pressures and caregiving responsibilities shaped whose learning was supported during lockdowns. These patterns highlight a common perception among rural teachers that the pandemic exacerbated pre-existing inequities related to household composition, financial vulnerability, and unequal distribution of parental attention and support.

Figure 20. *How families affect learning loss*

The perceptions of learning loss presented in [Figure 21](#) offer further insight into the specific learner groups rural teachers believed were most at risk. The top groups were students with limited access to technology (16%), students with special educational needs (16%), students from the poorest families (13%), and students whose parents could not help with school because of work or other obligations (12%). Many of these categories relate directly to the socioeconomic realities of rural communities, reflecting teachers' recognition that the greatest learning disruptions were experienced by those whose needs were already underserved or structurally marginalised before the pandemic. Teachers also highlighted instability at home, pre-existing low attainment, and language mismatch as compounding factors, suggesting that rural learners' needs were multi-dimensional, intertwining material, linguistic, developmental, and psychosocial elements.

Figure 21. *Learners perceived to have suffered more learning losses than other students*

Taken together, Figures 19–21 show that teachers perceived rural learners' pandemic-era needs as deeply rooted in structural disadvantage rather than deficits in individual capabilities. The most significant needs identified, i.e., reliable access to technology, consistent adult support for home learning, targeted intervention for learners with special needs, and strategies to compensate for household-level inequities, reflect systemic gaps that shaped how, and whether, learning could continue during school closures. These insights show that any programme for rural students must address not only how they are taught but also the broader support system, such as their homes, financial problems, and access to learning tools. In this context, teachers' perceptions indicate that the needs of rural learners during the pandemic were primarily related to inequity, influenced by social, economic, and infrastructural constraints that significantly affected their ability to engage in education.

While each research question highlights a different facet of teachers' experiences, the patterns that emerge across them point to deeper structural and contextual issues that extend beyond individual practices or

isolated constraints. [Section 4](#) draws these threads together, offering a set of key insights that synthesise the findings and illuminate their broader significance for rural education, professional development, and policy.

4. Key insights from the survey

Across the four research questions, the findings offer a coherent picture of how rural teachers and learners navigated education during the Covid-19 pandemic. These observations show that technology adoption gaps alone are not sufficient to describe rural education. Instead, rural teaching and learning were influenced by a constellation of infrastructural, socioeconomic, curricular, and pedagogical constraints that fundamentally shaped what was possible during school closures and reopenings.

First, the data reveals that rural teachers were strategically utilising technology within ecological constraints, rather than utilising it less. Messaging apps, short videos, and printed materials emerged as the most commonly used and valued tools because they were resilient to unstable networks, intermittent access, and shared devices. International research consistently reflects this trend, with educators in digitally disadvantaged environments demonstrating a preference for low-bandwidth, readily available tools that support learners with inconsistent access ([↑Beaunoyer et al., 2020](#); [↑Valencia-Arias et al., 2025](#)). Malaysian studies similarly document that rural and B40 learners struggled with maintaining stable connectivity, had limited device ownership, and often relied on family-shared phones ([↑Saidi et al., 2022](#)). These adaptations, therefore, reflect context-responsive professionalism, not technological reluctance.

Second, the limited use of more interactive digital pedagogies, such as collaborative activities, synchronous discussions, and digital feedback, was primarily shaped by structural digital inequalities rather than teacher preference. Rural teachers identified insufficient internet access, limited devices, and weak school-level support as the most significant barriers to effective instruction. These findings resonate with international literature documenting that rural digital divides often take the form of “nominal access but limited meaningful use” ([↑Esteban-Navarro et al., 2020](#), p. 12). In Malaysia, quantitative analyses of digital classroom usage similarly highlight statistically significant differences between rural and urban teachers in connectivity, infrastructure, and technical support ([↑Yap et al., 2024](#)). The results thus critique any deficit discourse that attributes rural digital practices to teacher attitudes, instead positioning them within broader sociotechnical infrastructures.

Third, rural teachers' professional development needs reveal a desire not simply for ICT skills but for context-sensitive, practice-embedded support. Teachers prioritised developing digital confidence, improving online

teaching, and integrating technology meaningfully into daily practice. This aligns with global findings that TPD initiatives during the Covid-19 pandemic were most effective when they were sustained, situated within classroom realities, and responsive to local constraints, rather than tool-driven workshops ([↑Hennessy et al., 2022](#); [↑Huang et al., 2024](#)). Rural-focused TPD studies further stress that training must acknowledge infrastructural limits and help teachers design for low-bandwidth, asynchronous environments ([↑Coker, 2021](#)). Malaysian research on Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) training indicates that cascade-model professional development frequently fails rural educators when it presumes resource-abundant, monolingual, or high-proficiency classrooms ([↑Chong & Yamat, 2021](#); [↑Shak et al., 2025](#)). Hence, effective TPD for rural teachers must foreground pedagogical design for constrained environments, teacher agency, and culturally and linguistically relevant practice.

Fourth, the finding that rural teachers were more likely to call for curriculum revision points to deeper systemic misalignment. Compared to their urban and suburban colleagues, rural teachers expressed a stronger conviction that the pandemic exposed curricular expectations as unrealistic for their learners. This aligns with criticisms of CEFR-aligned reforms in Malaysia, where imported materials, pacing expectations, and assessment requirements frequently do not accurately represent the linguistic repertoires, proficiency levels, and resource conditions of rural learners ([↑Bayuong & Hashim, 2023](#); [↑Shak et al., 2021](#)). Rural teachers' simultaneous call for more lesson-planning autonomy emphasises the importance of tailoring curricula to real-world conditions rather than implementing them uniformly.

Finally, teachers' perceptions of rural learners' needs reveal that learning loss was unevenly distributed and structurally produced. Teachers identified learners from low-income households, those with limited access to technology, children with many siblings, those with disabilities or special needs, and those with unstable home environments as the most vulnerable. These patterns mirror global findings that the Covid-19 pandemic exacerbated existing inequalities, disproportionately harming students with socioeconomic disadvantages, household crowding, and limited parental support ([↑Dorn et al., 2020](#); [↑Engzell et al., 2021](#)). Malaysian research indicates that B40 learners experienced greater online learning disruptions, had fewer parental educational resources, and encountered food or financial instability ([↑Devisakti et al., 2024](#)). Teachers' perceptions thus reflect a multidimensional understanding of learners' needs,

spanning material, cognitive, emotional, and relational aspects. These are needs that cannot be met through instructional strategies alone.

Across all findings, a consistent picture emerges. Rural teachers are active, adaptive professionals working within conditions of profound structural constraint, and rural learners' needs during the pandemic were shaped more by systemic inequities than by individual deficits. Supporting rural education, therefore, requires TPD, curriculum, and policy reforms that are equity-oriented, context-grounded, and attentive to the lived realities of rural schools, families, and communities.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

This survey provides a clearer understanding of how rural teachers and learners experienced technology-mediated education during the Covid-19 pandemic and what these experiences imply for future professional development and policy. Across the findings, a consistent message emerges: rural teachers demonstrated adaptability and professional judgement, yet their efforts were shaped, and often limited, by structural inequalities. These include unstable internet access, device scarcity, and socioeconomic vulnerability among learners.

Rural teachers' reliance on messaging apps, short videos, and printed materials reflected not a lack of digital readiness but a pragmatic response to their learners' circumstances. Their professional development needs, which focused on building confidence in digital pedagogy and integrating technology meaningfully, point to a desire to deepen practice rather than simply acquire technical skills. At the same time, their call for greater autonomy and curriculum revision reveals deeper misalignments between national expectations and the realities of rural teaching. Teachers' perceptions of learning loss further show that the pandemic disproportionately affected learners facing poverty, limited home support, special needs, or technological exclusion. These highlight that learning challenges were structurally produced.

Moving forward, supporting rural education requires solutions that recognise these contextual realities rather than apply uniform approaches. Three recommendations follow:

1. **Context-responsive professional development:** TPD should focus on low-bandwidth instructional strategies, practical models for collaboration and feedback, and sustained support rather than isolated workshops.
2. **Curricular flexibility and teacher agency:** Rural teachers should be supported in adapting pacing, materials, and assessments to learners' readiness, with national curricula that allow greater localisation.
3. **Structural investment and holistic support:** Essential prerequisites for equitable digital learning include improving connectivity, providing devices, and strengthening family and community support systems.

To summarise, the findings show that meaningful improvements in rural education require pedagogical, curricular, and structural reforms based on rural communities' lived realities. Achieving this will require coordinated efforts across teacher education, school leadership, and national policy, alongside continuous monitoring of rural experiences. By investing in contextually relevant and culturally responsive TPD and removing infrastructural barriers, Malaysia can move toward a more resilient and inclusive system capable of supporting all learners, during crises and beyond.

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<https://docs.edtechhub.org/lib/JJEVS297>

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Appendix: The T4 Teachers and Technology Global Survey

NOTE: Questions used in this study are highlighted through the use of bold font.

About you.

1. During the last 12 months, did you work as a schoolteacher?
2. What best describes your gender? Select one answer.
3. Select where you teach.
4. Do you have any long-standing illness, disability or infirmity?
(Long-standing means anything that has troubled you over a period of time or that is likely to affect you over a period of time.)

Yes | No | Prefer not to say

5. How many years of school teaching experience do you have?

Less than 2 years | 3 to 5 years | 6 to 10 years | 11 to 20 years | 21 to 30 years | More than 20 years

6. What is the highest qualification for teaching you have received?

About your school.

7. What type of area is your school located in? Select one answer.

8. What type of school do you teach at?

Public/State/Government funded/Charter/Academy school |
Private school | Low-cost private school | Religious school | Charity or
NGO funded school

9. Select your school's main curriculum

10. Describe the infrastructure usually available in your school

- My school has access to the internet

Yes | No

- All or most teachers have access to the internet at home

Yes | No

11. Which of the following best describes the digital devices usually available in your school? Select all answers that apply to you

- **My school does not have any digital devices**
- **My school has one computer/laptop/tablet for the school**
- **My school has one computer/laptop/tablet for each class**
- **My school has one computer/laptop/tablet or mobile device per teacher**
- **My school has one computer/laptop/tablet per child**
- **My school has digital devices available but none of them are working**
- **Teachers have to bring their own device**
- **Learners have to bring their own device**

About your learners.

12. What age are the learners you are teaching this year? Select all answers that apply to you.

0-4 years old | 5-7 years old | 8-11 years old | 12-16 years old | 17 years or older

13. If you are teaching at a secondary school or tertiary college/university, what subject(s) do you teach? Select all answers that apply to you.

- **Language studies/foreign languages (These are different from the main language you teach in and include language and literacy in a language that is not your mother tongue)**
- **Reading, writing, literacy, literature in your mother tongue or first language**
- **Mathematics**
- **Economics**
- **ICT and Computing (e.g. coding, information technology, electronics, graphic design, design technology, construction)**
- **Science (e.g. life science, biology, chemistry, physics, environmental science, engineering, surveying)**

- **Personal, Social and Health Education (e.g. health studies, grooming, hygiene, personal health & safety, social relationships, character)**
- **Business Studies (e.g. accounting, book keeping, human resources, marketing, project management, international business, operations)**
- **Physical Education (e.g. sport, physical education, gymnastics, dance)**
- **Domestic Sciences (e.g. cooking, knitting, sewing, home economics)**
- **Social and Human Sciences (e.g. psychology, law, community or contemporary studies, civic education, citizenship, environmental studies, legal studies, political science, anthropology, sustainability studies)**
- **Practical, Trade and Vocational Skills (These are skills that help prepare you for a specific job. e.g. mechanics, plumbing, electrical, childcare, hairdressing, tourism, driving, chef, welding, technician, fitting, fashion, hospitality, scaffolding)**
- **Religion/Ethics (e.g. religion, history of religions, religion culture, ethics)**
- **Arts (e.g. arts, music, visual arts, drama, photography, drawing, film, media studies)**
- **Humanities (e.g. geography, history, philosophy, theory of knowledge)**
- **I only teach in primary school**

14. Overall, how would you describe the socio-economic status of the learners at your school? Select all answers that apply to your school.

High socio-economic status | Medium socio-economic status | Low socio-economic status Teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic.

15. What happened to your school during the COVID-19 pandemic?

My school remained open throughout the pandemic | My school was open some of the time, but closed during lockdown(s) remained closed throughout the pandemic

16. You said that your school was closed during lockdowns. Were teachers able to undertake remote learning in those times? Select one answer.

Yes | No | Some of the time

17. Did you do any of the following in the COVID-19 pandemic?

- **Make printed copies of digital resources to share with learners**
- **Contact learners through messaging services (e.g. SMS, Whatsapp, other)**
- **Contact parents/caregivers through messaging services (e.g. SMS, Whatsapp, other)**
- **Contact parents/caregivers via phone**
- **Share lessons and tasks with learners by e-mail**
- **Contact parents/caregivers via email**
- **Make audio-recordings to share with learners**
- **Record instructional videos to share with learners**
- **Share lessons and tasks with learners using a school learning platform**
- **Teach classes online**
- **Teach learners online and face to face at the same time**
- **None of the above or no technology was used**

18. During the last 12 months, how often did you do the following activities?

Every day or almost every day | About once or twice a week | About once or twice a month | About once or twice a year | Never or almost never

- **Use digital resources to create lesson plans**
- **Use digital resources to design tasks**
- **Use digital resources to find instructional materials**
- **Use digital resources to explore new teaching methods**
- **Use digital resources to assign learning tasks**
- **Use digital resources to enable student collaboration**
- **Use digital resources to provide feedback to students**
- **Use digital resources to provide access to instructional material for students who cannot physically attend class**
- **Use digital resources to communicate with parents or guardians**

- **Use online tools or computer-based testing to assess students' learning**
- **Use digital resources to share ideas or resources with colleagues**
- **Take part in professional communities of practice online**

19. Did your school encourage you to use any digital resources for lesson planning and teaching?

Yes | No

20. Which digital resources did your school encourage you to use?

- Virtual Learning Environment/LMS (E.g. Seesaw, Blackboard, Canvas Edmodo)
- School or community interactive platform (E.g. ClassDojo)
- Video conferencing tools (E.g. Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, Skype)
- Digital textbooks
- Quiz tools
- Video resources (E.g. online/digital TV, YouTube)
- Audio resources (E.g. podcasts, audio recording, online/digital radio)
- Web-based resources (For example: Wikis, lesson plans, Other)
- Messaging and social media (For example: WhatsApp, SMS, Facebook, Messenger, other)
- Broadcast radio
- Broadcast television
- None of the above

21. Overall, how useful was the Virtual Learning Environment/LMS to your teaching?

Rating scale: 1 | 2 | 3

- **Overall, how useful was the School or community interactive platform to your teaching?**
- **Overall, how useful was the video conferencing tool to your teaching?**
- **Overall, how useful were the digital textbooks to your teaching?**
- **Overall, how useful were the quiz tools to your teaching?**
- **Overall, how useful were the video resources to your teaching?**

- Overall, how useful were the audio resources to your teaching?
- Overall, how useful were the web resources to your teaching?
- Overall, how useful was messaging and social media to your teaching?
- Overall, how useful was broadcast radio to your teaching?
- Overall, how useful was broadcast TV to your teaching?
- Overall, how useful were the other digital resources used to your teaching?

Current teaching challenges.

22. To what extent is this school's capacity to provide quality instruction currently hindered by any of the following issues? Select one answer per row.

Not at all | To some extent | Quite a bit | a lot

- Shortage of qualified teachers
- Shortage or inadequacy of instructional materials (For example: textbooks)
- Shortage or inadequacy of digital technology for instruction (For example: software, computers, tablets, smart boards)
- Insufficient internet access
- Shortage of support personnel
- Shortage or inadequacy of instructional space (For example: classrooms)
- Shortage or inadequacy of physical infrastructure (For example: classroom furniture, school buildings, heating/cooling, and lighting)

Learning loss and teaching post COVID-19.

23. What are your experiences with learners in your class(es)?

Agree | Disagree | Don't know

- All students continued to progress their learning
 - Some students have not progressed their learning
 - No students have progressed their learning
- a) You told us that some or none of your students have progressed their learning (or you didn't know). Have any of these things been affected?

Yes | No | Don't know

- Learners have less self-discipline or are less motivated to learn
- Learners' literacy skills have suffered
- Learners' numeracy skills have suffered
- Learners' communication and interpersonal skills have suffered
- Learners' confidence has suffered
- Learners' wellbeing has suffered
- Learners are finding it more difficult to pay attention during (in person or online) lessons
- Learners are choosing not to participate or they make less contribution in the lesson

b) Have you noticed anything else has been affected as a result of your students not being able to progress their learning during this time?

24. If your school reopened following closures for the COVID-19 pandemic, which of the following has taken place? Select all answers that apply to you.

- Assessment of students' learning levels
- The curriculum was adapted to meet students' learning levels
- Lessons focused on remediation/making up for lost learning
- None of the above

25. Have any of these groups of learners experienced more learning loss than other students?

- **Learners from the financially poorest households (including food poverty)**
- **Learners with physical disabilities, learning difficulties or other special needs**
- **Learners who have been displaced from their home**
- **Learners whose mother tongue/first language is not the language of instruction**
- **Learners with less access to the internet or technology**
- **Learners who have experienced illness or bereavement in their families due to COVID-19**
- **Learners who have experienced financial difficulty or unemployment in their families due to COVID-19**
- **Learners who had low levels of attainment prior to the pandemic**

- **Learners who have an unstable home background**
- **Learners whose parents/caregivers have been unable to support them in their lessons outside school (e.g. because they are working)**
- **Learners that you consider to be vulnerable or have other needs/special requirements**

26. In your experience over the past 12 months, are any of these true?

a) Girls have experienced more learning loss than boys

Yes | No | Don't know

b) Parents/caregivers have prioritised boys learning over girls during lockdown

Yes | No | Don't know

c) Parents/caregivers prioritised older children's learning over learning of younger children

Yes | No | Don't know

d) Boys have experienced more learning loss than girls

Yes | No | Don't know

e) Single children have experienced more learning loss than children with many siblings

Yes | No | Don't know

f) Children with many siblings have experienced more learning loss than single children

Yes | No | Don't know

27. Have you noticed any other groups of learners who have had a poorer quality or reduced learning experience compared to others?

Yes | No | Don't know

28. What should your school do post COVID-19 in teaching, pedagogies or structurally to help learners to catch up? Select all answers that apply.

- **Help learners understand how they can learn better and develop independent learning strategies**
- **Introduce more play in learning to reduce stress**

- Give learners more time to practice and reflect, rather than relying solely on direct instruction
- Allow for more peer-to-peer learning and interaction in the classroom/remotely
- Engage parents/caregivers more frequently
- Add more hours or days to teaching time
- Provide more opportunities (time, financing, training) to use technologies for individualised learning
- Reduce class sizes
- Reduce administration to focus on teaching and learning
- Provide more direct instruction
- Focus on specific group(s) of marginalized/vulnerable learners who experienced learning loss
- Give teachers more autonomy to deliver lessons targeted to the learners' needs and learning levels
- Allow teachers more freedom in lesson planning
- Support socio-emotional learning
- Introduce remedial tutoring

29. What should governments do post-COVID-19 to address any loss of learning experienced?

- Promote the teaching profession in order to increase the number of teachers
- Focus on teacher recruitment and retention
- Support teachers' wellbeing
- Support teacher development/teacher training
- Revise curriculum
- Provide digital access and devices for marginalised learners (e.g., learners from low-income households, SEND learners, girls, minority language learners)
- Provide more technology for individual learning by those who need more support
- Provide more materials for digital teaching and learning to schools
- Provide training and support for teachers to better integrate technology into education
- Cancel exams and replace them with regular assessment and monitoring
- Collect learning outcomes data to monitor progress over the long term
- Provide support for socio-emotional learning

Your professional learning.

30. During the past 12 months did you take part in any form of teacher professional development or training (organised or self-initiated)?

Yes | No

a) You told us that you took part in teacher development or training in the past 12 months. Who paid for the cost of it?

- the school
- the government
- self-funded

b) You told us that you took part in teacher development or training in the past 12 months. What did it focus on?

- Using technology tools and resources for online or remote teaching and learning (including audio, video, broadcast radio and TV, WhatsApp, etc.)
- Pedagogies for online or remote teaching and learning
- Progress monitoring during remote learning
- Learner safeguarding online and during remote learning
- Safe online behaviour for teachers
- Understanding online learner behaviour
- Engaging parents/caregivers during remote learning
- Engaging in teacher communities of practice
- Teachers' physical, mental and/or emotional wellbeing

c) You told us that the focus of your professional development or training was the use of technology tools and resources for online teaching. What kind of tools or resources did you learn about?

- Virtual Learning Environment/LMS (E.g. Seesaw, Blackboard, Canvas Edmodo)
- Video conferencing tools (E.g. Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, Skype)
- Digital textbooks
- Quiz tools
- Video resources (E.g. online/digital TV, YouTube)
- Audio resources (E.g. podcasts, audio recording, online/digital radio)

- Web-based resources (E.g. Wikis, lesson plans, etc.)
- Messaging and social media (E.g. WhatsApp, SMS, Facebook)
- Broadcast media (E.g. radio, TV)
- School or community platforms (E.g. ClassDojo)

31. Think back across the (organised or self-initiated) professional development or training you experienced over the last 12 months (on any topic). Overall, to what extent did your practice change as a result?

Rating scale: 1 | 2 | 3

32. How much time in total was spent on your professional development or training over the last 12 months? Add up the actual time you spent and answer in whole days.

33. An extensive global platform might be developed over the coming year where teachers can share classroom practices with others outside their regions. Would you consider using this to share teaching resources and lesson plans that you have created yourself?

Yes | No

34. Which is NOT the type of school you teach at?

Public/State/Government funded/Charter/Academy school |
Private school | Low-cost private school | Religious school | Charity or
NGO funded school

Your needs as a teacher.

35. Which of the following areas could support your teaching in the next 12 months? Select up to five (5) answers maximum.

- Teaching online/remotely
- Caring for my mental health and wellbeing
- Developing skills and confidence in using digital technologies in teaching
- Subject/content knowledge for my own professional development
- Pedagogy/teaching methods for my own professional development
- Curriculum-related for my own professional development
- Integrating digital technologies into classroom practice

- Protected time during the working week for professional development and peer collaboration
- More interactive or engaging learning resources
- Assessment and monitoring of learners
- Safeguarding
- More administrative support
- More social or peer encouragement from people in your school
- Engaging in (remote) communities of practice with other educators
- Tackling gender issues related to learners' technology use
- Teaching/adapting to marginalised learners' needs (e.g. students with disabilities; minority language speakers; displaced, orphaned or otherwise vulnerable students)
- Coaching/mentoring
- No support needed

36. What further support could help you in the next 12 months?

37. Do you need more access to software or other (non-hardware) digital resources for the following tasks? Select one answer per row.

- My professional learning. Yes | No
- Planning lessons. Yes | No
- Assessment and evaluation. Yes | No
- Learners to use themselves (e.g. worksheets, quizzes, digital textbooks). Yes | No

38. Which of these statements best describes the quality of your teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic? Select one answer.

The experience has had no impact on your teaching quality | The experience has made you a better teacher | The experience has made you a worse teacher

39. How do you feel about teaching since the pandemic started?

About the same | Less enthusiastic | More enthusiastic

- a) You told us you were more enthusiastic about teaching now. Why?
- b) You told us you were less enthusiastic about teaching now. Why?

40. How would you describe the level of respect/esteem that parents/caregivers have for teachers since the pandemic started? Select one answer.

About the same | More respect/esteem | Less respect/esteem

41. How would you describe what has happened to your physical, mental and emotional wellbeing since the pandemic started? Select one answer.

My wellbeing has improved | My wellbeing has suffered | My wellbeing is about the same

42. Which of these statements best describes your current plans in the teaching profession?

I am undecided about my teaching plans | I plan to leave the teaching profession | I plan to remain a teacher

43. How likely are you to recommend teaching to friends, family or others?

Rating scale: 1 | 2 | 3